

THE CITY OF GENERAL TRIAS EGALITARIAN ADVOCACY TOWARDS AN INCLUSIVE AND EMPOWERED SENIOR CITIZENS COMMUNITY

Ernest R. Vera Cruz, DPA

*Professorial Lecturer, Public Administration, Graduate School of Business
University of Perpetual Help System Dalta, Las Pinas Campus, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This paper explored the policies and initiatives of the City of Gen. Trias by scaling its egalitarian advocacy towards one of its marginalized sectors, the Senior Citizens, examining the key elements that enabled the city to foster more inclusive and empowered community, while also drawing insights from relevant case studies and best practices from the Philippine setting and beyond. The study builds framework that proposes a comprehensive strategy for the City of General Trias to balance its advocacy efforts and create a more inclusive and empowered community for its senior citizens. The findings suggests that the local government must shortened bureaucratic obstacle by adopting Information Technology (IT) in barangay-level administrative system to shorten the lengthy procedure and record redundancy, ensuring safety and mobility of older adults, designing an inclusive transportation system to improve the autonomy and independence of the elders, allowing senior citizens to navigate their surroundings with ease and confidence.

Keywords:

Senior Citizen, Inclusivity and Empowerment, Local Governance, Egalitarian Advocacy, Local Government Unit (LGU), City of Gen. Trias (GenTri), R.A. 9994, Office of Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA),

INTRODUCTION

The City of General Trias, situated in the province of Cavite, Philippines, has long been a beacon of egalitarian ideals, striving to create a community where the principles of inclusivity and empowerment are at the forefront of its civic endeavors. As the city continues to grow and develop, it faces the challenge in implementing its egalitarian advocacy to ensure that its commitment to creating an inclusive and empowered community remains steadfast and impactful. At the heart of the city's egalitarian efforts lies a deep-rooted understanding that true progress can only be achieved when all members of the community are given equal opportunities to participate, contribute, and thrive.

As the population of the City of General Trias continues to grow, it is crucial to address the needs and concerns of its senior citizen community. Advocacy efforts aimed at empowering and supporting this demographic can have a significant impact on the overall well-being and inclusivity of the city.

Allowing older adults to "age in place" - to comfortably remain in their familiar homes and communities as they grow older - is a critical consideration, as research indicates that elders who are able to do so are reported to enjoy a higher quality of life, greater social connectedness, and fewer health care complaints than those who do not (Ratnayake, et al., 2022). However, smaller communities like that of General Trias, which are experiencing an influx of elders from urban and rural areas, may face strain on municipal services and a diminished economic activity if they do not successfully manage the challenges of an aging population (Azzali et al., 2022).

To address these challenges, the city adopted the City Ordinance No. 16-13 (Special) granting cash incentive to any senior citizens in the City of General Trias who are 90 to 99 years old upon the effectivity of this Ordinance on July 17, 2017.

However, the city's COMPREHENSIVE DEVELOPMENT PLAN 2020-2029 never mentioned of policy or program that offers LGUs tangible benefits for senior citizens. An approach that would involve multi-agency collaborative governance structure that brings together city officials, urban planners, community organizations, and older adults themselves is needed to collectively develop and implement a comprehensive set of age-friendly policies and initiatives tailored to the unique needs and context of General Trias (Hossen et al., 2023).

This collaborative model is exemplified in Singapore's Kampung Admiralty development, where a diverse set of stakeholders worked together to create a mixed-use community that seamlessly integrates residential, commercial, and healthcare services to support the city's growing population of older residents (Azzali, et al., 2022).

Likewise, the World Health Organization's framework for age-friendly cities provides a valuable blueprint for identifying and addressing the key features that contribute to an inclusive and empowered senior community, such as adjusting the built environment to

accommodate mobility needs, ensuring access to affordable healthcare, transportation, medicine, recreation, and creating opportunities for social engagement and civic participation (Levin, et. al. 2022).

This paper explored the policies and initiatives utilized by scaling its egalitarian advocacy towards its Senior Citizens, examining the key elements that enabled the city to foster more inclusive and empowered community, while also drawing insights from relevant case studies and best practices from the Philippine setting and beyond. This likewise builds framework that proposes a comprehensive strategy for the City of General Trias to balance its advocacy efforts and create a more inclusive and empowered community for its senior citizens.

Research Questions

The City of General Trias faces the challenge of addressing the needs and empowering its growing senior citizen population towards an inclusive community. Understanding the lived experiences and perspectives of the Filipino elderly can provide insights to guide the city's advocacy efforts. Existing research on the experiences of the Filipino elderly offers valuable perspectives that can inform the development of effective policies and programs to support this population.

Exploring, therefore, the attitudes and perceptions of Senior Citizens living in the city founded upon their strong cultural values, and the economic challenges stemming from their ageing status will facilitate the LGU to coin a better policy framework towards their inclusion and empowerment in the community.

This paper specifically answered the following questions:

1. What are the tangible and intangible benefits for senior citizens derived from egalitarian advocacy of the local government of the City of General Trias, Cavite?
2. Do the Senior Citizens fully enjoy these tangible and intangible benefits implemented by the LGU?
3. What experiences and perceptions these diverse elderly adults can share in their participation and representation to local governance of the City of General Trias?
4. What strategic framework can the SC suggests improving the egalitarian advocacy of the City of General Trias?

Theoretical Lens

The existing literature on senior citizen benefits highlights the complex nature of the challenges faced by the aging population, underscoring the need for a comprehensive and multifaceted approach to address the diverse needs of this demography.

As the global population continues to age, the importance of understanding and addressing the unique needs and challenges faced by senior citizens has become increasingly paramount. Governments and policymakers must take initiative to ensure

that the aging population is provided with the necessary resources and support to maintain a high quality of life. One key aspect of this is addressing the issue of income insecurity among the elderly (Sidani et al., 2017).

The global aging phenomenon has placed immense pressure on social services and public infrastructure, with potential economic impacts as well. Fortunately, the development of "smart city" technologies offers new opportunities to address the challenges of an aging population (Zhang, 2021).

Researchers have emphasized the importance of enabling older adults to remain in their homes and communities as they age, a concept commonly referred to as "aging-in-place" (Oliveira et al., 2018).

Inoue, et. al. (2024) underscored that one critical area of concern is the issue of income insecurity among the elderly. Many older adults struggle with financial challenges, such as a lack of access to sufficient pension and retirement funds, which can lead to a deterioration in their overall well-being. To address this, governments should explore a variety of financial instruments and initiatives, including improving financial literacy and developing robust pension fund infrastructure, to provide seniors with the financial security they require.

Rudnicka, et. al. (2020) emphasized that access to healthcare is another pressing issue that must be addressed. Healthy older individuals often contribute significantly to their communities, both financially and through unpaid work, and it is in the best interest of society to ensure that they have access to the medical care they need. However, many elderly individuals face barriers to healthcare, such as social isolation and neglect, which can have detrimental effects on their health outcomes.

Furthermore, research suggests that senior citizens may face difficulties in adapting to new technologies, such as smart devices, which can limit their ability to engage with digital content and services (König, et al., 2016). Therefore, efforts should be made to develop user-friendly interfaces and educational resources to help elderly individuals navigate and utilize these technologies.

The concept of egalitarian advocacy for community empowerment has been extensively explored in academic literature, with researchers delving into the theoretical underpinnings, practical applications, and societal implications of this approach (Malta, 2023).

Empowerment, as a central tenet of egalitarian advocacy, is widely recognized as a planned effort designed to change or reform an individual or community/society from a state of powerlessness to become empowered with an emphasis on independence (Malta, 2023). This process involves a fundamental shift in power dynamics, where marginalized communities are equipped with the critical consciousness and agency to challenge existing inequalities and work towards a more just and equitable society (Cornwall, 2016).

One key aspect of egalitarian advocacy is the recognition of the inherent value and capabilities of all members of a community, regardless of their socioeconomic status, gender, or other demographic factors. This principle is particularly relevant in the context of empowering senior citizens, who are often sidelined and marginalized in many societies (Manuere, et. al., 2018). Demographic transitions and population aging have brought to the forefront the need to build an inclusive culture that enables the elderly to lead a dignified and fulfilling life (Paltasingh, et. al., 2012).

The academic literature emphasizes the importance of holistic approaches to the empowerment of senior citizens, encompassing not only their material well-being but also their intellectual, physical, and spiritual development (Massie, et. al. 2019).

A community work approach, which fosters strong connections between the elderly and their local communities, has been identified as a particularly effective method in this regard. This approach aims to transform the perception of the elderly from "passive clients" to "active and empowered individuals", thereby enhancing their self-image, advocating for their rights, and increasing their influence in policy-making processes (Kelchner, 2002).

Recognizing the critical role of education in shaping societal attitudes towards the elderly, researchers have advocated for a multifaceted approach that integrates the strengths perspective, critical social construction, and a human rights and social justice focus into the government's policies and programs (Paltasingh, et. al, 2012).

The literature also highlights the importance of addressing the specific challenges faced by marginalized and underprivileged senior citizens, regardless of their socioeconomic background (Carandang, et. al., 2019). This calls for the development of a comprehensive support framework that can enable the elderly to lead a quality life with dignity, considering the unique needs and circumstances of each individual or community (Wagiman, et. al., 2016)

The conceptual and empirical insights provided by the academic literature on egalitarian advocacy and senior citizen empowerment offer a solid foundation for the development of inclusive and equitable policies and programs that can empower this segment of the population (Rijal, 2023).

Literature also highlights the role of pedagogical approaches in empowering the elderly, advocating for a focus on the strengths and capabilities of older adults, a critical understanding of how social constructions shape perceptions of aging, and a commitment to human rights and social justice (Patterson, 2004).

By adopting a multifaceted approach to empowerment, which addresses both structural and individual-level barriers, egalitarian advocacy can contribute to the creation of a more inclusive and supportive environment for senior citizens, enabling them to age with dignity, autonomy, and a sense of belonging within their communities (Cheng, 2020).

Furthermore, literature advocates for a humanistic view of aging, which challenges the negative stereotypes and marginalization often associated with the elderly (Dionigi, 2015).

Researchers have also highlighted the critical role that healthcare professionals, social workers, and other stakeholders can play in advocating for the rights and needs of senior citizens (Lubkina, et. al., 2013). By adopting a humanistic view that recognizes the inherent worth and agency of the elderly, these professionals can help to combat the negative stereotypes and stigma often associated with aging and empower older adults to become active participants in their own care and in the shaping of their communities (Kaye, et.al., 2023).

METHODOLOGY

Research design

A qualitative research design was used in this study. The qualitative method enables an in-depth assessment of the egalitarian advocacy of the City of General Trias, Cavite Province. In-depth interviews and focus group discussions (FGD) with the senior citizens were used to get insights into the experiences and attitudes of the policies and programs implemented by the city.

Research locale

The respondents were wide-ranging group of elderly residing in selected Barangays of the City of General Trias, particularly: Pasong Camachile II; Pasong Kawayan I; Bacao II; Santiago; and San Francisco. Purposive sampling was utilized to guarantee that the results reflected diverse profile of genders, age groupings, and socio-economic backgrounds. Nine (9) elderly individuals and one (1) focus group from the five selected Barangays were interviewed and assembled to discuss the predetermined topics mentioned in the research questions.

Research instrument

An interview guide, and a focus group discussion guide were among the research tools. During the interviews and focus group sessions, these instructions were utilized to assist in-depth exchanges.

Data gathering procedure

Face-to-face interviews and focus group discussions were used to gather data. The interview and focus group discussions were conducted by the researcher and audio-recorded with the participants' agreement. Raw data was transcribed, place in matrices and translated from Filipino to English.

Data analysis

Thematic analysis was used to find common themes and patterns in the responses from the qualitative data. Coding the data, recognizing themes, analyzing, and refining the themes, and eventually defining and naming the themes are all part of this process. The researcher did the analysis manually, using the Microsoft word and was guided by the research questions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. TANGIBLE AND INTANGIBLE BENEFITS FOR SENIOR CITIZENS DERIVED FROM EGALITARIAN ADVOCACY OF THE LOCAL GOVERNMENT

Senior Citizens ID Card an Essential Life-Saving for Elderly Adults

“Since I was given a Senior Citizens ID card, I have not felt any tangible benefits (i.e., financial subsidies) from the City government of Gen Trias except discounts from purchases of medicine and grocery items. I don’t perceive that the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) had any program here in our city or at least in our barangay.”

-KRI1

“We only rely on the discounts through our SC ID card provided by the local government. We have not felt any financial assistance or at least a birthday gift from the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) of the city.”

-FGD1

Situated in the picturesque province of Cavite, the City of General Trias houses the Senior Citizens Affairs Office (OSCA) that plays a crucial role in issuing identification cards to senior citizens within its jurisdiction. These ID cards serve as a vital tool in ensuring that the elderly population of General Trias can access the various benefits and services provided by the local government, as well as national programs and initiatives aimed at improving their quality of life.

This is a testament to the city's commitment to ensuring the well-being and dignity of its older residents. The Office of Senior Citizens Affairs of General Trias is at the forefront of this endeavor, providing a comprehensive range of services and programs tailored to the unique challenges and requirements of the city's senior population (Cahapay, 2021).

However, the current landscape of support and benefits available to the senior citizens of General Trias, with the objective of pinpointing areas where the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) can enhance its service delivery to better cater to the needs of the local elderly population. The prompt highlights the concerns raised by a local senior citizen, who expressed dissatisfaction with the limited financial assistance provided

by the government, beyond the standard discounts offered through their senior citizen ID cards. This suggests that the current efforts by the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) may not be enough to fully address the diverse needs and expectations of the senior citizens in the area.

Existing research on the topic suggests that while the benefits mandated by the RA 9994, or the Expanded Senior Citizens Act of 2010, are essential in helping senior citizens cope with financial challenges, they are often merely palliative measures (Gerolin et. al., 2020).

The Philippine government has established various laws and policies aimed at enhancing the well-being of senior citizens, including the provision of identification cards and diverse discounts (Carandang et al., 2019). However, the responsibility for caring for the elderly still predominantly rests on Filipino families, rather than the government. This notion is reflected in the Philippine constitution, which states that "The family has the duty to care for its elderly members, but the State may also do so through just programs of social security". Nonetheless, the rising costs of basic necessities, education, healthcare, and recreational activities often compel Filipino families to prioritize the needs of younger or employed members over the elderly . Consequently, the unmet needs of community-dwelling senior citizens in the Philippines remain substantial.

Access to Healthcare for Elderly Adults in Barangay Health Centers

There is a free medical check-up in our barangay health center but we have to be patient with the long ques because, aside from us, there were also other patients.

-KRI2

In our barangay, medical check-up is not done daily because we believe that there is a deficiency of medical and health practitioners of the city. Sometimes doctors are in rotation form one barangay to other.

-FGD2

As the population of senior citizens continues to grow, particularly in the provinces, ensuring their access to high-quality healthcare services becomes increasingly vital (Magtangob, et. al., 2023). The Philippine government must prioritize enhancing the healthcare system, especially for vulnerable populations like senior citizens, to promote healthy aging. In recent years, the Chinese government has made strides in improving the accessibility of healthcare services for the elderly, and the Philippine government could learn from their approach (Di, et al., 2020).

The barangay health centers in General Trias City provide free medical check-ups for elderly adults, which is a positive step towards improving healthcare access. However, the fact that these check-ups are not conducted daily means that during emergency situations, elderly adults may still be constrained to seek care at expensive private hospitals (Magtangob, et. al., 2023). This limitation in the availability of free healthcare

services for the elderly population could have significant implications for their overall health and well-being.

The senior citizens population in the Philippines accounts for about 8.8% of the total national population, according to the 2023 census data (ESCAP, 2024). While there are reports of improving functional health and increasing life expectancy among Filipino senior citizens, there are also significant gaps in their health status (Cahapay, 2021). The General Trias government's provision of senior citizen identification cards, while a positive gesture, does not appear to translate into tangible benefits or address the fundamental needs of this demographic. (Carandang et al., 2019)

Need for Free Maintenance Medicine

“For me, I always buy my own medicine from a commercial drugstore, I do not intend to beg for my maintenance medicine from the city government because some elderly told me that there are only limited stocks, and you keep on going back to the City Hall.

-KRI3

Free medicine is not often available for elder adults. Sometimes we have to go to the Mayor's office to obtain a free medicine but is oftentimes busy with his administrative tasks

-FGD3

The provision of free medicine for elderly adults in various barangays in General Trias City is not sufficient. This issue requires immediate attention as it has significant implications for the health and well-being of the city's aging population.

The need for improved access to free medicine for the elderly in General Trias City is underscored by several factors. Firstly, the Philippines is experiencing a rapid aging of its population, with the proportion of individuals aged 60 and above expected to reach 15.9% by 2045 (Magtangob, et. at., 2023). This demographic shift underscores the growing importance of addressing the healthcare needs of senior citizens, particularly in terms of access to essential medications.

Magtangob, et. al. (2023) further stressed that the increasing access to high-quality healthcare, including the provision of free medicine, is of the utmost importance in emerging countries like the Philippines, and the government needs to be committed to enhancing the healthcare system, especially for vulnerable populations like senior citizens.

2. SENIOR CITIZENS' PERCEPTION OF TANGIBLE AND INTANGIBLE BENEFITS IMPLEMENTED BY THE LGU

Lack of Awareness and Limited Availment of the Benefits Provided by Law

The truth is that, I'm not quite familiar with the tangible benefits provided by the LGUs. Maybe, there are, but no one is telling me about those aids or subsidies. I merely enjoy the discounts on my purchases of medicines, groceries, and foods in restaurants.

-KRI4

Even in our barangay, there are no notifications about the benefits of seniors. Sometimes there are rumors that the LGU will provide us Five Hundred Pesos (PhP500.00) monthly stipend, but until now, by the God's Grace, we have not tasted [received] anything yet. We think these are just fake news.

-FGD4

The plight of senior citizens in accessing the tangible and intangible benefits implemented by local government units is a pressing concern that requires thorough examination. While these benefits are intended to improve the quality of life for the elderly, the reality on the ground suggests that senior citizens do not fully enjoy these provisions (Gerolin & et. al., 2020).

One of the critical challenges faced by senior citizens is the lack of awareness and limited availment of the benefits provided by the law. While the majority of senior citizens were aware of the benefits, a significant number did not fully avail themselves of these entitlements. This disconnect between awareness and utilization highlights the need for more effective outreach and education efforts to ensure that senior citizens are empowered to access the resources available for them.

Furthermore, the existing benefits afforded to senior citizens, such as discounts on essential goods like food and medicine, as well as the provision of a social pension, are often inadequate to address the profound financial challenges faced by this population. Many senior citizens and their supporting families live below the poverty line, and these benefits, while helpful, are merely palliative measures that fail to provide a comprehensive solution to their needs.

The study by Cablao et al., (2019) also underscores the importance of exploring the specific needs and preferences of senior citizens in order to tailor the assistance and services provided by local government units. This personalized approach is crucial in ensuring that the benefits and services delivered truly address the diverse and evolving needs of the elderly community.

3. THE EXPERIENCES AND PERCEPTIONS OF DIFFERENT SENIOR CITIZENS IN THEIR PARTICIPATION AND REPRESENTATION IN LOCAL GOVERNANCE OF GENERAL TRIAS CITY.

Establishment of a Resolute Senior Citizens' Advisory Councils

Actually, nobody tells me to participate in a senior citizens' club in our barangay. I don't feel like there is a senior's organization here that's why I cannot also participate in the activities if there are.

-KRI5

At first, there were activities here in our barangay, we were quite active before like having slight physical exercise every morning. Today, we often spend time together at GenTri People's Park where we can breathe fresh air, discuss things related to our comorbidities (laughs). But now, it seems that our senior citizens officers are no longer active in our city.

-FGD5

As local governments strive to be more inclusive and representative, understanding the experiences and perceptions of different stakeholder groups, such as senior citizens, becomes crucial. This paper explored the participation and representation of senior citizens in the local governance of General Trias City, providing insights into the barriers, challenges, and opportunities they face (Ramasamy, 2020).

The study draws from existing literature on public participation in local government administration, which highlights the importance of inclusive decision-making processes for successful policy implementation and community development. Analogous to the findings from Libon, Albay, this research uncovered the Indigenous perspectives and experiences of senior citizens in General Trias City, recognizing their unique role and contributions to local governance. Additionally, the study acknowledges the need for local communities to have a voice in development decisions to ensure their needs and concerns are adequately addressed (Michael et al., 2013).

Lack of Appropriate Communications

As I have told you, no one cares to inform me about the programs and activities of senior citizens organization in our city or even barangay.

-KRI6

Yes, in our barangay, the elderly adults don't even care to bother asking our officials about the activities of the OSCA. Barangay officials concern only their programs and projects such as basketball, volleyball tournaments, clean and green projects where sometimes SC are involved but when it comes to the concerns of the elderly, it is nothing.

-FDG6

The findings of this study reveal the challenges faced by senior citizens in actively participating in local governance, such as limited accessibility to decision-making processes, lack of effective communication channels, and perceived exclusion from policy discussions. However, the research also highlights the willingness and desire of senior citizens to be more involved in the decision-making processes that shape their community, echoing the sentiments expressed in the literature on the public's preferred level of involvement in local policy-making. (Haesevoets et al., 2023)

Moreover, the study identified key factors that contribute to the underrepresentation of senior citizens in local governance, including a lack of targeted outreach and engagement efforts by the local government, as well as societal perceptions of the elderly as passive or disengaged citizens.

4. IMPROVING EGALITARIAN ADVOCACY IN THE CITY OF GENERAL TRIAS FOR SENIOR CITIZENS' INCLUSIVITY

Conduit to Active Participation

I hope the officers of Senior Citizens' Organization will become active again to motivate all members to be aware and become dynamic with all their activities. It would be good to note that an active officers will always encourage members to follow suit.

-KRI7

If the officers would become active in their participation with the City Council, then perhaps they can make representation to the city government so that the senior citizens' plight will be heard. It seems that they don't have the influence to approach the Mayor to voice out our concerns.

-FGD7

One critical aspect of this policy framework is the establishment of formal mechanisms for senior citizen participation. This could involve the creation of resolute advisory councils or committees that provide a platform for older adults to voice their concerns, offer insights, and influence the development and implementation of relevant policies and programs. Such institutionalized channels of engagement not only empower senior citizens but also ensure that their needs and interests are systematically incorporated into the governance process.

Across the Philippines, the Office of Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) operates under the auspices of the mayor's office, with the primary mandate of facilitating the distribution of senior ID cards, which are required for accessing various discounts and services (Carandang et al., 2019).

However, the law also enables local government units to expand the scope of subsidized offerings for the elderly, based on the specific concerns of their aging

constituents. It is only the local government who knows and understand the problems of their own constituents.

Therefore, it is essential that local government officials proactively engage with senior citizens to understand their unmet needs and preferences, and then channel this information to the city council to drive meaningful policy changes.

Enhanced Infrastructure for PWDs and Senior Citizens and Navigating Bureaucratic Obstacles

In fact, the Office of the OSCA is found at the People's Park. When I applied for an ID, I though the OSCA can be found at the city hall, only to find out that it is situated in the People's Park. The OSCA staff let me go back and forth from the park to city hall and vise-versa to secure documents like Election Certificate, copy of my Birth Certificate from the Civil Registrar's Office and again to the barangay to secure for a Barangay Certificate spending my hard earned money for my expensive transportation.

-KRI8

OSCA used to be on the 4th floor of the city hall but later transferred to the People's Park. It is now very inconvenient to secure SC ID because the remoteness of the offices that issued certificates and necessary documents. It's just pleasing their staffs, who are not SC themselves, are very cordial in entertaining us.

-FGD8

As an individual seeking to secure important documents, the process of navigating bureaucratic systems can be a daunting and often frustrating experience. The OSCA staff's willingness to allow the individual to travel back and forth between the park and city hall, as well as the barangay, to gather the necessary documents, such as the Election Certificates and a copy of the Birth Certificate from the Civil Registrar's Office, highlights the challenges that many citizens face when attempting to fulfill administrative requirements.

The emerging trend towards the use of information technology in barangay-level administrative systems, as outlined in the "Barangay Constituents Information and Services Management System" study, suggests that the manual processes currently in place contribute to lengthy procedures and record redundancy (Kevin et al., 2018).

Results has shown that senior-friendly tourism destinations, which prioritize factors like reliable public transportation, senior-friendly outdoor spaces, and accessible buildings, can significantly enhance the quality of life and well-being of older travelers (Liew et al., 2021). Similarly, in the context of urban planning, policymakers must prioritize age-friendly approaches that guarantee equal access to essential services and activities for the elderly population (Guida et al., 2022).

Safety and Mobility, A call for Local Government Intervention

I observed that there is a lack of access roads and safe pedestrian lanes for elderly and PWDs. Perhaps the local government will initiate the improvement of these pedestrian lanes and signages.

-KRI9

Our roads and streets at the moment are not safe for pedestrians. We mean all pedestrians, more reason that these infrastructures are hazardous to those who are physically challenged, children and the elderly. We hope that the engineering department including those city departments who are concern with the safety of people in the streets will find ways to improve by providing pedestrian lanes for crossing and sidewalks. As if we are racing with cars, trucks and other vehicles while traversing these areas.

-FGD9

Another crucial factor is ensuring the safety and mobility of older adults within the city. Designing communities with a focus on inclusive transportation systems and pedestrian-friendly infrastructure can greatly improve the autonomy and independence of senior citizens, allowing them to navigate their surroundings with ease and confidence. (Liew et al., 2021).

Mobility-related challenges, including unsuitable building design, transportation barriers, and unsafe sidewalks or curbs, can severely limit the community participation of seniors and individuals with disabilities. Children, older adults, and those with physical or cognitive impairments often rely more heavily on non-motorized travel modes, making them more vulnerable to the consequences of inadequate pedestrian and bicycle facilities. In light of these challenges, it is crucial to understand the impact of community design on individual mobility and identify the key stakeholders responsible for creating mobility-supporting environments.

To address the mobility needs of an aging population, a collaborative effort involving a diverse range of professionals, such as occupational therapists, architects, urban planners, and transportation engineers, is essential. These individuals can work together to design communities that prioritize the safety and accessibility of pedestrian infrastructure, ensuring older adults can access essential services and maintain their independence (Sandt et al., 2016).

One approach to evaluating the accessibility of urban services for older adults is the 2SFCA (two-step floating catchment area) method, which considers both the supply and demand of services, as well as the mobility features and behavioral traits of the elderly population (Guida et al., 2022).

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following were derived:

1. The National and local government has established various laws and policies to enhance the well-being of senior citizens, however, these are only palliative measure. The responsibility for caring the elderly still rest upon the shoulder of the member of the family rather than the government.
2. There are existing benefits afforded to the senior citizens such as discounts on essential goods, medicines as well as provision of social pension are often inadequate the profound financial challenges faced by this demographic population.
3. Although the paper highlighted the willingness of the senior citizens to be more involved in the decision-making of the City, however, there are challenges faced by them such as limited accessibility to decision- making process, lack of effective communication with the SC officers, and the perceived exclusion from policy discussions and debates.
4. The findings suggests that the local government must shortened bureaucratic obstacle by adopting Information Technology (IT) in barangay level administrative system to shorten the lengthy procedure and record redundancy, ensuring safety and mobility of older adults, designing an inclusive transportation system to improve the autonomy and independence of the elders, allowing them to navigate their surroundings with ease and confidence.

Recommendations

Based on the theme analysis and results, the following suggestions were made to improve the egalitarian initiatives of the City of General Trias towards the empowerment and inclusivity of senior citizens community in the city:

1. One key aspect to address the unfelt tangible benefits for the LGU is the need to improve overall awareness and empathy for older persons, as well as strengthen local government capacity for their integration. This humanistic approach can help eradicate the marginalization of senior citizens and promote their everyday competence, dignity, and well-being.
2. Innovations in information technology using internet or the smart phones that will enhance the well-being of elderly people by addressing their daily life needs, health, and emergency situations.
3. To address these challenges, the research proposes a series of recommendations, such as the establishment of resolute senior citizen advisory councils, the implementation of inclusive communication strategies, and the provision of capacity-

building opportunities to empower senior citizens to participate more actively in local decision-making processes.

4. To this end, the city of General Trias should consider the following recommended policies:
 - a. Implement a comprehensive public transportation system that caters to the needs of senior citizens, with features such as easy-to-access shuttle buses, electric trikes with comfortable seating, and clear signage;
 - b. Develop a network of well-maintained, accessible sidewalks and crosswalks that prioritize the safety and mobility of children, PWDs, and older pedestrians;
 - c. Encourage the construction of senior-friendly buildings and public spaces, with features like ramps, handrails, and ample seating areas exclusive for children, elderly, and PWDs;
 - d. Establish community centers in every barangay and programs and activities that provide seniors with opportunities for social interaction, lifelong learning, and physical activity, thereby enhancing their overall well-being and sense of belonging.
 - e. Encourage and require the Office of the Senior Citizens Affairs (OSCA) to submit a Comprehensive Strategic Plan for the consideration of the City Council as legislative measure for the SC empowerment and inclusivity within the City of Gen. Trias Community;
 - f. By adopting these age-friendly policies, the city of General Trias can create an inclusive and supportive environment that empowers senior citizens to actively participate in their community and enjoy a high quality of life.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Qualitative research has become increasingly prominent in various academic and professional fields, offering valuable insights into complex human experiences and behaviors. However, the inherent nature of qualitative research, which often involves in-depth interactions with participants, raises important ethical considerations that researchers must navigate.

One of the primary ethical challenges in qualitative research is the issue of informed consent. The researcher ensured that the participants fully understood the purpose of the study, the potential risks and benefits, and their right to withdraw at any time. This can be particularly challenging in dynamic and flexible qualitative studies, where the research process may evolve over time.

The researcher was very diligent in maintaining continuous consent, regularly checking with participants to ensure their understanding and willingness to continue.

Additionally, the issue of confidentiality and the protection of participants' privacy is of paramount importance in qualitative research. The researchers ensured that sensitive information is securely stored, and that participants' identities are protected, even in cases where the research topic may be politically or socially charged.

Ethical dilemmas may also arise in the context of qualitative research involving vulnerable populations, such as children, the elderly, or those with mental health issues (Taquette, et. al., 2022).

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Thank you, Mayor Luis “Jun Jun” Ferrer III, my fraternal brother in the GLP F&AM.

“Let us ignite the spirit of inclusivity and empowerment of the marginalized sector in our beloved city”

To my family, mommy JO, ate AC and our bunso OBIT, and most of all to our Lord Almighty!

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